

Solvation Free Energies in Subsystem Density Functional Theory

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Supporting Information

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1 Additional Data

The violine plots and convergence plots for the solvation free energies of the compounds in the Claisen rearrangement in water and in cyclohexane are shown in Figs. S1 and S2, respectively, for all sampling approaches. The convergence plots for the free energies of activation for the Menshutkin reaction in water, the Claisen rearrangement in water, and the Claisen rearrangement in cyclohexane are given in Fig. S3. The corresponding convergence plots for the reaction free energies are shown in Fig. S4.

Figure S1: Solvation free energies for the reagent (a), the transition state (b) and the product (c) of the Claisen rearrangement in water derived with the four different combinations of sampling strategy and method (bottom). The first four rows show the distribution for each evaluated combination, indicated by color, the fifth row represents the direct comparison between the four approaches.

Figure S2: Solvation free energies for the reagent (a), the transition state (b) and the product (c) of the Claisen rearrangement in cyclohexane derived with the four different combinations of sampling strategy and method (bottom). The first four rows show the distribution for each sampling approach, indicated by color, the fifth row represents the direct comparison between the three sampling approaches.

Figure S3: Free energies of activation for the Menshutkin reaction (a), the Claisen rearrangement in water (b) and in cyclohexane (c) derived with the four different combinations of sampling strategy and method. The first four rows show the convergence and error as well as a 4.18 kJ/mol window, the fifth row represents the direct comparison between the four investigated strategies.

Figure S4: Free energies for the Menshutkin reaction (a), the Claisen Rearrangement in water (b) and in cyclohexane (c) derived with with the four different combinations of sampling strategy and method. The first four rows show the convergence and error as well as a 4.18 kJ/mol window, the fifth row represents the direct comparison between the four sampling approaches.